

GAPS

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

The Financialisation of the EU Governance of Return and Readmission

Concept Note

Authors:

N. Ela GÖKALP ARAS and Umutcan YÜKSEL

Swedish Research Institute in Istanbul, SRII

D9.1–January 2026

Funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by

UK Research
and Innovation

Canada Excellence
Research Chair in
Migration & Integration

Deliverable Information

Project acronym	Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond
Project no.	101094341
WP	9
Deliverable title	WP9/ D9.1 (Concept Note)- “The Financialisation of the EU Governance of Return and Readmission”
Deliverable type	R – Document, report
Version	v1
Date	January- 2026
Responsible partners	Swedish Research Institute in Istanbul (SRII)
Authors	N. E. Gökalp Aras and Umutcan Yüksel
Dissemination level	Public

Revision History

Version	Date	Authors	Changes
V1	07.01.2026	N. Ela Gökalp Aras, Umutcan Yüksel	The first draft was submitted to the WP9 co-leaders and the consortium coordinators.
V2	12.01.2026	N. Ela Gökalp Aras, Umutcan Yüksel	Final version submitted.

© SRII

This research was conducted under the Horizon Europe project “GAPS: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond” (101094341). The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to the author at ela.gokalparas@sri.org.tr; umutcan.yuksel@sri.org.tr

Cite as:

Gökalp Aras, N. E. and Yüksel, U. (2026). “The Financialisation of the EU Governance of Return and Readmission”, WP9 Concept Note on the Policy and Financial Dimension of Returns and Readmissions in GAPS Working paper 2026/07. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18234528

1. Introduction

The European Union's (EU) efforts to manage migration beyond its borders have long relied on diplomacy, legal agreements, and conditional cooperation. Over the past two decades, however, financial instruments have become a central element of this strategy, functioning as a form of soft power through which the EU externalises migration governance and shifts responsibilities to third countries. In the early 2000s, migration occupied a marginal position within the EU's external budgets, with funding largely directed toward small-scale capacity-building and regional protection programmes and limited emphasis on return or readmission (Tsourdi *et al.*, 2023).

This configuration changed progressively from the mid-2000s onward and decisively after the 2015 "refugee crisis," when migration management, particularly return and readmission, was embedded as a core priority within the EU's external financial architecture. Instruments such as the EU Trust Fund for Africa, the Facility for Refugees in Turkey, and later the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument-Global Europe (NDICI-GE) illustrate this shift (Tsourdi *et al.*, 2023; Xanthopoulou, 2024). Financial instruments thus evolved from supportive tools into active mechanisms of externalisation, conditioning cooperation, and outsourcing border control, returns, and readmissions to third countries.

This concept note examines how the EU's financial architecture operates as a tool of migration diplomacy, with a particular focus on return and readmission governance. It asks how EU financial instruments have evolved in the fields of migration and asylum, how they shape the external dimension of return and readmission, and how they embed EU priorities within third countries' migration infrastructures and policy frameworks. The study argues that funding is not merely a technical or humanitarian mechanism but a strategic instrument through which the EU operationalises externalisation in politically sensitive domains such as return and readmission.

While the literature on EU migration governance has extensively examined externalisation, it has largely focused on legal, institutional, and political instruments (Lavenex & Uçarer, 2002, 2004; Boswell, 2003; Xanthopoulou, 2024), migration diplomacy and bargaining (Greenhill, 2010; Tsourapas, 2017; Adamson & Tsourapas, 2019), differentiated cooperation (Stubb, 1996; Lavenex, 2006, 2015; Holzinger & Schimmelfennig, 2012; Leuffen *et al.*, 2013; Schimmelfennig *et al.*, 2015; Müftüler-Baç, 2019; Holzinger & Tosun, 2019; Okyay *et al.*, 2020; Gökalp Aras, 2021), or conditionality-based critiques (Schimmelfennig & Sedelmeier, 2004; Frelick *et al.*, 2016; Carrera *et al.*, 2019). The financial dimension of externalisation has only recently emerged as a distinct analytical focus (Tsourdi *et al.*, 2023).

A growing body of work examines funding more directly, highlighting how EU financing has become a core instrument of externalisation through earmarking, conditionality, and attenuated accountability (Tsourdi *et al.*, 2023; Tsourdi & Zardo, 2025). Other studies show how financial arrangements link economic support to cooperation on migration control and readmission (Strik & Robbesom, 2024), and how third countries actively appropriate EU funding to strengthen domestic capacity and diplomatic leverage (Laube, 2021; Gökalp Aras, 2019a, 2019b, 2024; Ovacık *et al.*, 2022; Şahin Mencütek *et al.*, 2023; Vollmer & Şahin-Mencütek, 2023; Ulusoy, 2025). Despite these advances, a systematic understanding of how funding operates specifically as a tool of externalisation in the return domain remains limited. This concept note addresses this gap by tracing the evolution of EU financing for migration externalisation, with particular attention to return and readmission. Adopting a decentring approach, it recognises the agency of third countries and conceptualises externalisation as a co-produced process shaped by negotiation, adaptation, and resistance. The chapter concludes by highlighting the implications of this financialised mode of governance for transparency and accountability in EU migration policy.

2. Methodology

The concept note employs a multi-level document analysis, combining qualitative analysis of policy documents, financial reports, and human rights assessments with the systematic consolidation of financial data. Drawing on a material discourse analysis approach (Jessop, 2010; Sum & Jessop, 2013) and the political economy of quantification (Mügge, 2016), funding allocations are treated as material expressions of policy priorities. At the macro-level funding architecture (Global Level), EU programming documents are analysed to map instruments and thematic allocations. At the instrument level, NDICI-GE project data for 2021–2024 are coded by thematic focus and operational impact, using an instrumental lens (Lascoumes & Le Galès, 2007).

A key limitation arises from the fragmented and overlapping nature of EU migration funding. Instruments such as the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF), the EU Regional Trust Fund in Response to the Syrian Crisis (MADAD), the Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance (IPA) and the NDICI-GE often co-finance or absorb one another, complicating project-level tracking and longitudinal analysis. Limited public data and the absence of a unified database constrain transparency, particularly regarding return-related expenditure, necessitating triangulation across scattered sources.

3. Development of Funding for Externalisation and Returns

The EU externalisation in migration and asylum has developed through multiple tools and strategies, ranging from political declarations to legal agreements and operational cooperation. The instruments regarding collaboration with third countries in the field of immigration and asylum can be classified into three groups: “political instruments”, “legal instruments”, and “operational instruments” (IPOL, 2015). Departing from their categorisation, one more category needs to be considered: “financial instruments” (Gökalp Aras, 2021). Legal instruments that embed migration clauses into association and cooperation agreements or conclude specific readmission and visa facilitation agreements (such as the EU-Ukraine Visa Facilitation and Readmission Agreement, the EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement). Political instruments include regional and bilateral dialogues (such as the Prague Process, the Rabat Process, and the Khartoum Process) and compacts with key countries such as Jordan, Lebanon, and Turkey. They also include Operational instruments that further complement these approaches through Regional Protection Programmes (RPPs, such as RPP for Eastern Europe/ Belarus, Moldova, Ukraine, 2005) and Regional Development and Protection Programmes (RDPPs, such as RDPP North Africa/ Egypt, Libya, Tunisia, Morocco, 2015), which seek to strengthen asylum capacity in third countries.

On the other hand, financial instruments have become a central pillar of externalisation, enabling the EU to indirectly operationalise migration control, return, and readmission through support, capacity-building, and development aid. Initially, migration-related funding was channelled through instruments. Over time, these funds increasingly targeted operational areas such as irregular migration control, border management equipment, and readmission cooperation.

The periodisation of funding in the EU’s externalisation policy, with a special focus on funding, can be classified into four periods as follows:

3.1. First Period (1990-2003): Legal Foundations with Limited Financial Leverage

Since the late 1990s, the EU has intensified cooperation with non-EU countries on migration and mobility, with the 1999 Tampere European Council providing the first programmatic orientation, though with limited financial backing (McGregor *et al.*, 2025). During this phase, migration clauses were gradually attached to cooperation agreements, and modest financial

incentives were introduced to encourage readmission commitments (IPOL, 2015; Gökalp Aras, 2021).

Pre-accession instruments for candidate countries (PHARE/1989-2006; ISPA/2000-2006; SAPARD/2000-2006) occasionally financed border control and administrative capacity through twinning projects, but they lacked a dedicated migration or return package. For non-candidate countries, migration-related funding was channelled through development and neighbourhood instruments, notably the European Development Fund (EDF), whose scope gradually expanded in the late 1990s to include projects addressing root causes of migration and small-scale reintegration (European Parliament, 2014; European Commission, 2020a). However, return and readmission remained marginal and weakly articulated.

Similarly, the Euro-Mediterranean Partnership (MEDA, 1996-2006) focused primarily on development cooperation with North Africa and the Middle East, while gradually incorporating components of border management and migration dialogue (European Union, 2006a; Natorski, 2008). Overall, this period laid the legal and policy groundwork for externalisation, but financial instruments remained limited, fragmented, and embedded within broader development aid rather than migration-specific funding envelopes.

3.2. Second Period (2004-2014): Institutionalisation of Migration Funding

Following the 2004 enlargement, the EU introduced more structured financial instruments for migration governance. Earlier pre-accession tools paved the way for IPA I (2007-2013), which explicitly included migration governance and funded return-related infrastructure, such as reception facilities and biometric systems, in line with EU standards (European Commission, 2025a). This shift was reinforced by the Hague Programme (2004), which formally prioritised cooperation with third countries on migration (European Council, 2005a).

Migration funding also became more visible through the Global Approach to Migration (GAM, 2005), later expanded into the Global Approach to Migration and Mobility (GAMM) in 2011 (European Council, 2005b; European Commission, 2011). Mobility Partnerships, launched in 2007, operationalised this framework by linking legal mobility facilitation with cooperation on irregular migration, return, and readmission (European Commission, 2016). In parallel, the European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument (ENPI, 2007-2013) financed asylum capacity-building and border control in neighbouring countries, often tied to readmission clauses (European Union, 2006b).

A key development for the return dimension was the creation of the European Return Fund (ERF, 2008-2013), the first dedicated EU instrument supporting assisted voluntary return, reintegration, and cooperation with third countries (European Council, 2007; European Commission, 2014). While the Return Directive provided the legal framework (European Council, 2008), the ERF operationalised it financially. Although formally internal, ERF implementation linked the EU's internal return regime to its externalisation agenda through readmission cooperation, including the EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement signed in 2013. By the end of this period, migration (particularly return) had become a distinct and visible budgetary priority (Lavenex, 2006; IPOL, 2015; Trauner & Kruse, 2008).

3.3. Third Period (2014-2020): Crisis-Driven Expansion and Differentiation

The post-2015 period marks a decisive turning point in EU externalisation. Whereas earlier externalisation relied mainly on legal mechanisms, such as Schengen, Dublin, and formal readmission agreements (Halvik, 2019; Lavenex, 2006), the 2015 refugee crisis triggered a shift toward crisis governance, soft-law arrangements, and large-scale funding packages (Gökalp Aras, 2021, 2024). The EU-Turkey Statement (2016) exemplifies this shift, linking substantial financial transfers under the Facility for Refugees in Turkey (FRIT) and post-FRIT

to return cooperation and containment objectives (European Council, 2016; Kassoti & Carrozzini, 2022).

During this period, migration funding expanded through instruments such as the European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI, 2014-2020), IPA II (2014-2020), EU Trust Funds (MADAD; EUTF), and the AMIF (2014-2020). These tools financed border management, return infrastructure, reintegration programmes, and operational cooperation with third countries, including capacity-building for readmission (ICMPD, 2019). New operational mechanisms also emerged, such as European Return Liaison Officers and the European Return and Reintegration Network (ERRIN), later integrated into Frontex's expanded mandate (European Commission, 2015; European Court of Auditors, 2021; ICMPD, 2025a).

From 2014-2020, the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) consolidated earlier funds into larger, flexible envelopes, while ad hoc instruments proliferated in response to the crisis. Migration funding shifted from a supportive role to a strategic lever of conditionality, increasingly tied to deterrence, return rates, and cooperation outcomes (Tsourdi *et al.*, 2023; Nicolosi, 2024). This period is characterised by the financialisation of externalisation, with funding prioritising border control and returns over protection and reintegration (Carrera *et al.*, 2019; Gökalp Aras, 2021; Xanthopoulou, 2024).

3.4. Fourth Period (2021-Present): Integrated and Conditional Funding under the New Pact

Since 2021, the EU externalisation funding has entered a consolidated phase with the adoption of the NDICI-GE, which merged previously fragmented instruments into a single, flexible framework (European Commission, 2021b; European Commission, 2021c). At least 10% of its envelope is allocated to migration and forced displacement, explicitly linking funding to return and readmission cooperation (Tsourdi *et al.*, 2023). The NDICI-GE operationalises the New Pact on Migration and Asylum by embedding migration conditionality into development, trade, and foreign policy partnerships (European Commission, 2020b; European Commission, 2024).

This period is marked by outcome-oriented, tailor-made partnerships, supported by NDICI-GE, AMIF (2021-2027), IPA III (2021-2027), and the Integrated Border Management Fund, including the Border Management and Visa Instrument (European Commission, 2021a). These instruments finance return infrastructures, biometric systems, joint return operations, and cooperation platforms with third countries, often coordinated by Frontex. Talent Partnerships and Team Europe Initiatives further illustrate how legal migration schemes are explicitly conditioned on cooperation in return and readmission (Boubakri *et al.*, 2025; Lahlou & Belhaj, 2025; Uzomah *et al.*, 2025).

Overall, the post-2021 period reflects a maturation of funding-driven externalisation: integrated, conditional, and normalised. Financial instruments now function simultaneously as incentives and enforcement tools, embedding return governance within broader development and security frameworks (Gökalp Aras, 2021; Nicolosi, 2024).

Table 1: Evolution of EU Externalisation Funding for Return and Readmission

Period	Timeframe	Dominant Logic	Key Financial Instruments	Role of Funding in Return & Readmission
I. Legal Foundations	1990-2003	Normative and legal groundwork	PHARE, ISPA ¹ ,	Migration clauses embedded in cooperation and development frameworks; limited, indirect, and fragmented funding for migration;

¹ ISPA stands for the Instrument for Structural Policies for Pre-Accession

			SAPARD ² , EDF, MEDA	return and readmission not yet a distinct financial priority
II. Institutionalisation	2004-2014	Formalisation and visibility of migration funding	IPA I, ENPI, ERF, GAM/GAMM; Mobility Partnerships	Migration governance becomes a visible budgetary line; first dedicated return instrument (ERF); funding enables implementation of the Return Directive and supports readmission cooperation.
III. Crisis-Driven Expansion	2014-2020	Emergency governance and differentiated externalisation	ENI; IPA II; AMIF; EUTF; MADAD; FRIT; ERRIN	Funding shifts from supportive to strategic leverage; large, ad hoc packages tied to deterrence, return rates, and cooperation outcomes; return and containment prioritised
IV. Integrated Conditionality	2021-present	Funding-driven, outcome-oriented partnerships	NDICI-GE; AMIF (2021–27); IPA III; IBMF/BMVI; TEIs ³	Financial instruments fully integrated into external action; return and readmission conditionality mainstreamed into development, trade, and mobility partnerships

Source: Prepared by authors based on the research.

4. Financial Analysis Findings

Through our financial analysis, we tracked six major instruments at the macro-level funding architecture (Global Level), along with a list of the NDICI-GE and Migration & Forced Displacement tools at the instrument level, which refer to the operational funding instruments (Instrument Level). The following table reflects those.

Table 2: Comprehensive Mapping of the EU Migration Funding Across Two Analytical Levels

Dataset Level	Time Period	Funding Instrument	Amount	Description
Macro-level Funding Architecture (Global Level)	2014-2027	AMIF, BMVI, NDICI-GE, EUTF, MADAD, ISF ⁴	€35.6 billion	6 major instruments in the EU's migration management
Operational Funding Instruments (Instrument Level)	2021-2024	NDICI-GE	€9.71 billion	221 projects

Source: Prepared by authors based on European Commission 2023a, 2023b, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, 2025g.

4.1. Macro-level Funding Architecture (Global Level)

Our systematic document analysis of the EU migration and border management funding at the macro level covers the MFF period from 2014 to 2027. We identify six major instruments, amounting to €35.6 billion in EU budget spending between 2014 and 2027, targeting migration and border management across both internal and external dimensions. AMIF, the Border Management and Visa Instrument (BMVI), and the ISF (Internal Security Fund) primarily regulate the EU's internal migration management while also enabling cooperation

² SAPARD stands for the Special Accession Programme for Agriculture and Rural Development

³ TEIs stands for the Team Europe Initiatives

⁴ The purpose of this table is to provide an overview of how migration-related expenditure is situated within the broader landscape of EU funding. However, it does not distinguish between the EU's internal and external funding architectures. In practice, AMIF, Border Management and Visa Instrument (BMVI), and the ISF (Internal Security Fund) constitute internal instruments, designed for use by Member States to support asylum systems, border management, and internal security. By contrast, NDICI-Global Europe, the EU Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF), and the MADAD Trust Fund are external instruments, directed towards third countries and used to finance cooperation on migration management, development, and humanitarian assistance beyond EU borders.

with partner countries. By contrast, NDICI-GE (since 2021) and EU Trust Funds (2014–2020) primarily address the external dimension.

In 2020, the European Commission proposed a total budget of €40.62 billion for migration and asylum programmes under the MFF 2021–2027, allocating €31.12 billion to the internal dimension and approximately €10 billion to the external dimension—representing a 78% increase compared to the MFF 2015–2020 (EuroMed Rights, 2020). Within the overall MFF 2021–2027 envelope of €1,210.9 billion (European Commission, 2025b), €25.6 billion is dedicated to Heading 4: Migration & Border Management, marking the first time this policy area has received a standalone budget heading. This funding is channelled mainly through the AMIF (European Commission, 2023a) and the IBMF (European Commission, 2023b).

Within this framework, the Migration Partnership Facility (MPF) supports cooperation between Member States and partner countries in migration-producing regions, including the Western Balkans, Sub-Saharan Africa, the Eastern Partnership, the Southern Neighbourhood, and Silk Route countries (ICMPD, 2025b). The BMVI funding may also be deployed in partner countries for equipment and training related to external border management, often alongside Frontex operations. In addition, the ISF complements AMIF and IBMF by addressing internal security objectives, such as combating human trafficking and migrant smuggling, thereby reinforcing the externalisation dimension of EU migration governance (European Commission, 2025f).

The NDICI-GE represents the EU’s most significant instrument for financing the external dimension of migration governance and for implementing the New Pact on Migration and Asylum. Introduced under the MFF 2021–2027, NDICI-GE merged ten previous external financing instruments into a single framework to enhance strategic coherence. With a total budget of €79.5 billion, €9.81 billion (12%) has been contracted under the migration management and forced displacement window (European Commission, 2025b). Finally, the EU Trust Fund for Africa (European Commission, 2025c) and MADAD (European Commission, 2025d) illustrate the role of extra-budgetary and extraordinary funding tools prior to their consolidation under NDICI-GE.

Figure 1: Timeline of Funding Instruments (In Billions of Euros)

Source: Visualised by authors based on data from European Commission 2023a, 2023b, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, 2025g.

In terms of key findings, our systematic document analysis shows that EU funding for migration and border management underwent a major transformation between 2014 and 2027, with six core instruments amounting to €35.7 billion. AMIF, BMVI, and ISF primarily govern the internal dimension of EU migration management, while NDICI-GE (since 2021) addresses the external dimension. Within the 2021–2027 MFF, €25.7 billion is allocated to the first dedicated Migration & Border Management heading, of which approximately 75% supports border control, return, and externalisation measures, compared to 25% for asylum and integration (EuroMed Rights, 2020).

The consolidation of previously “extraordinary” instruments, including EUTF, MADAD, and FRIT, into NDICI-GE’s €9.71 billion migration window institutionalised and streamlined the EU’s externalisation approach (European Parliament, 2021). However, Oxfam’s analysis of NDICI-GE-funded migration projects in Libya, Tunisia, and Niger raises concerns regarding ODA eligibility and the prioritisation of EU domestic migration objectives over development goals (Oxfam, 2023). These concerns are compounded by limited transparency, which constrains effective monitoring and democratic scrutiny of NDICI-GE migration spending (Pope & Weisner, 2023).

4.2. Development Cooperation Funding (Instrument Level)

On 14 June 2021, the NDICI-GE was adopted with a total allocation of €79.5 billion in EU development funding, covering almost all external partners. It finances the European Neighbourhood (excluding Turkey, funded through IPA III), including Eastern Partnership and Southern Neighbourhood countries, as well as Sub-Saharan Africa, the Middle East, Asia, Latin America, the Caribbean, and the Pacific. Beyond bilateral allocations, NDICI-GE also supports regional organisations, international organisations, and global thematic programmes in areas such as human rights, migration governance, climate change, and digital transformation. For the first time, approximately 10% of NDICI-GE funding was allocated to migration-related actions (Tsourdi *et al.*, 2023). A quantitative analysis of 221 projects shows that €9.71 billion committed between 2021 and 2024 under the migration management and forced displacement window represents 12% of the total NDICI-GE budget (European Commission, 2025b).

The funding distribution reflects a comprehensive yet uneven approach to migration governance. Protection and forced displacement initiatives dominate (63.02%), followed by migration and border management (15.96%) and return and reintegration (7.86%). Root causes programming accounts for 5.80%, while legal migration and labour mobility remain marginal at 2.09%, indicating that deterrence-oriented measures continue to outweigh facilitation despite policy commitments.

Figure 2: Thematic Focus of NDICI-GE Projects

Source: Prepared by authors based on EC data (European Commission, 2025b)

To assess how the European Union operationalises return and reintegration within its external migration governance, it is essential to examine the temporal dynamics of funding under the NDICI-GE framework. Rather than reflecting a stable or linear policy commitment, allocations in this thematic area provide insight into how financial instruments respond to shifting political priorities, external crises, and dynamics of cooperation with third countries. Analysing annual variations in funding levels and project allocations, therefore, allows for a closer understanding of the strategic and contingent nature of EU engagement in return-related externalisation. Figure 3 presents the evolution of NDICI-GE funding for the “Return and Reintegration” thematic area between 2021 and 2024.

Figure 3: Return and Reintegration Thematic Area under NDICI-GE Funding by Year (2021-2024)

Source: Prepared by authors based on EC data (European Commission, 2025b)

Figure 3 shows the annual variation in EU funding and project allocation for external migration initiatives, highlighting the changing intensity of financial engagement in return-related and externalisation activities. The peak in 2022 (€375M, 12.48%) indicates a surge in funding and project activity, followed by a sharp decline in 2023 (€47.7M, 2.5%) and a moderate recovery in 2024 (€178M, 6.37%). This fluctuation reflects the episodic and reactive nature of EU financial commitments, often linked to political priorities and external migration pressures. These year-to-year fluctuations in NDICI-GE allocations for the “Return and Reintegration” thematic area are not random but structurally embedded in the instrument’s design and political function. First of all, the NDICI-GE operates through highly flexible annual reprogramming across thematic and geographic envelopes. It means that funds can be shifted each year in response to evolving priorities. Second, the instrument includes a crisis-response mechanism that triggered significant budgetary reallocations following major geopolitical events, such as the collapse of Afghanistan in 2021, the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, and subsequent crises in Sudan and the Sahel. Third, most NDICI-GE actions are financed through multiannual project cycles, so disbursements tend to cluster in specific years depending on when large return or reintegration programmes are approved or become operational. Fourth, EU cooperation on return is profoundly shaped by political conditionality: when negotiations with key third countries such as Tunisia, Egypt, Bangladesh, Pakistan, or Niger are progressing well, budgetary allocations increase; when relations deteriorate, they decline or are suspended. Finally, the return programmes are often dependent on the capacity of implementing partners such as IOM and on the willingness of third countries to cooperate, which also results in these fluctuations.

Conclusion

This study has shown how EU financial instruments have progressively transformed migration governance beyond Europe, shifting funding from a technical support mechanism to a central tool of externalisation. Through a multi-level analysis, we demonstrate that funding has become a key medium through which the EU governs mobility at a distance. While financial instruments do not replace diplomatic, legal, or operational forms of cooperation, they increasingly operate alongside them as mutually reinforcing mechanisms that structure incentives, capacities, and dependencies in EU-third country relations.

The evolution of EU funding, particularly in relation to return and readmission, reveals a shift from broad development instruments to targeted, flexible, and strategically designed mechanisms, such as trust funds, differentiated pre-accession envelopes, and crisis-response tools. This shift reflects not merely a budgetary adjustment but a reconfiguration of the EU’s external action architecture, in which financial instruments function as a core modality for externalising migration governance. Through funding, the EU steers cooperation, shapes incentive structures, and redistributes responsibilities for return and readmission beyond its borders.

At the macro-level funding, these findings situate EU externalisation within a broader international trend of delegating migration control through financial and political incentives. Migration diplomacy increasingly links aid, trade, and security cooperation to migration control, with funding playing a constitutive role in shaping return infrastructures and aligning third-country policies with EU priorities.

At the instrument level, the consolidation of funding mechanisms marks a decisive shift. While early extraordinary tools responded to displacement through protection-oriented measures, their integration under NDICI-GE has institutionalised a control- and containment-oriented funding logic. Our analysis of 221 NDICI-GE projects (€9.71 billion) shows that protection rhetoric frequently conceals externalisation objectives: the majority of projects serve border control and containment functions, while rights-based protection remains marginal. This instrumental evolution mirrors the EU’s broader policy shift, reinforced by the New Pact, from

protection-centred to return-centred governance, raising concerns about accountability, transparency, and compliance with human rights.

Overall, EU funding-driven externalisation has produced a multi-scalar system of return governance that is global in reach and increasingly routinised in its instruments. These dynamics risk entrenching containment-focused infrastructures, permanent temporality, and stratified vulnerabilities in third countries. Addressing these challenges requires stronger accountability mechanisms, greater transparency, and the systematic integration of rights-based benchmarks into EU migration funding frameworks.

References

- Adamson, F. B., & Tsourapas, G. (2019). "Migration Diplomacy in World Politics." *International Studies Perspectives*, 20(2), 113–128. <https://doi.org/10.1093/isp/eky015>
- Boswell, C. (2003). "The 'External Dimension' of EU Immigration and Asylum Policy." *International Affairs*, 79(3), 619–638. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2346.00326>
- Boubakri, H., Ben Othmen, H. & Jedidi, M. (2025). "Return Migration Infrastructures in Tunisia". WP3 Country Report in GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. Working paper 2025/21. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15852188, https://zenodo.org/records/15852188/files/D3.1_WP3_Tunisia_Contry_Dossier.pdf?download=1
- Carrera, S., Santos, J. V. and Strik, T. (2019). "The External Dimensions of EU Migration and Asylum Policies in Times of Crisis." In *Constitutionalising the External Dimensions of EU Migration Policies in Times of Crisis* (Sergio Carrera, Juan Santos Vara, and Tineke Strik eds.), the UK: Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 1-19. <https://www.elgaronline.com/edcollchap/edcoll/9781788972475/9781788972475.00007.xml>
- EuroMed Rights. (2020). EU Migration Budget: More Border Management, Less Respect for Human Rights. <https://euromedrights.org/publication/eu-migration-budget-more-border-management-less-respect-for-human-rights/>
- European Commission. (2011). The Global Approach to Migration and Mobility (COM(2011) 743 final). Brussels: European Commission. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0743>
- European Commission. (2014). Final Report on the Implementation of the European Return Fund 2008–2013. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/return-fund-2008-13.html?fromSummary=23>
- European Commission. (2015). European Commission (2015). EU Action Plan on Return, COM(2015) 453 final, 9 September 2015. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52015DC0453>
- European Commission. (2016). Mobility Partnerships, Visa facilitation and Readmission Agreements, https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/internal-security/international-affairs/engagement-partner-countries/eastern-partnership/mobility-partnerships-visa-facilitation-and-readmission-agreements_en
- European Commission. (2020a). European Development Fund (EDF). Retrieved from https://international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/funding/european-development-fund-edf_en
- European Commission. (2020b). A New Pact on Migration and Asylum. COM(2020) 609 final. https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/migration-and-asylum-new-pact_en
- European Commission. (2021a). "European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI)". https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-06/db_2021_programme_statement_european_neighbourhodd_instrument_eni.pdf
- European Commission. (2021b). 2021-2027 Long-term EU Budget & NextGeneration EU, https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/eu-budget/long-term-eu-budget/2021-2027_en

- European Commission. (2021c). Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument – Global Europe (NDICI – Global Europe), https://enlargement.ec.europa.eu/funding-technical-assistance/neighbourhood-development-and-international-cooperation-instrument-global-europe-ndici-global-europe_en
- European Commission. (2023a). Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (2021-2027). https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/funding/asylum-migration-and-integration-funds/asylum-migration-and-integration-fund-2021-2027_en
- European Commission. (2023b). Integrated Border Management Fund – Border Management and Visa Instrument (2021-27). https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/funding/borders-and-visa-funds/integrated-border-management-fund-border-management-and-visa-instrument-2021-27_en
- European Commission. (2024). Pact on Migration and Asylum: Final Adoption and Implementation Guidelines. Brussels: Council of the European Union. https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/pact-migration-and-asylum_en
- European Commission. (2025a). “Overview - Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance”. https://enlargement.ec.europa.eu/enlargement-policy/overview-instrument-pre-accession-assistance_en
- European Commission. (2025b). Migration and Border Management Heading of MFF 2021-27. Retrieved 11 May 2025, from https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/eu-budget/long-term-eu-budget/2021-2027/spending/headings_en#heading-4-migration-and-border-management
- European Commission. (2025c). NDICI-Global Europe actions on migration and forced displacement. https://international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/document/download/7002229d-6be3-4efb-99b7-9fcboae665dd_en?filename=NDICI-Global%20Europe%20actions%20on%20migration%20and%20forced%20displacement.pdf
- European Commission. (2025d). Objective and Governance. EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa. https://trust-fund-for-africa.europa.eu/our-mission/objective-and-governance_en
- European Commission. (2025e). EU Regional Trust Fund in Response to the Syrian Crisis. https://trustfund-syria-region.ec.europa.eu/index_en
- European Commission. (2025f). Migration Management. https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/migration-management_en
- European Commission. (2025g). Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (2021-2027), https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/funding/asylum-migration-and-integration-funds/asylum-migration-and-integration-fund-2021-2027_en
- European Council. (2005a). The Hague Programme: Strengthening Freedom, Security and Justice in the European Union (2005/c 53/01), [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52005XG0303\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52005XG0303(01))
- European Council. (2005b). Global approach to migration: Priority actions focusing on Africa and the Mediterranean, <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-15744-2005-INIT/en/pdf>
- European Council. (2007). Decision No. 575/2007/EC of 23 May 2007 establishing the European Return Fund for the period 2008–2013 as part of the General Programme “Solidarity and Management of Migration Flows”. Official Journal of the European Union, L144/45, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2007:144:0045:0065:EN:PDF>
- European Council. (2008). Directive 2008/115/EC on Common Standards and Procedures in Member States for Returning Illegally Staying Third-country Nationals. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008L0115>

- European Council. (2016). “The EU-Turkey Statement”, 18 March 2016, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2016/03/18/eu-turkey-statement/>
- European Court of Auditors. (2021). Special Report No. 17/2021 – EU Readmission Cooperation: Implementation of EU Readmission Agreements. https://www.eca.europa.eu/Lists/ECADocuments/SR21_17/SR_Readmission-cooperation_EN.pdf
- European Parliament. (2014). “European Development Fund”, <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/EPRS/EPRS-IDA-542140-European-Development-Fund-FINAL.pdf>
- European Parliament. (2021). Implementation report on the EU Trust Funds and the Facility for Refugees in Turkey (Report No. A9-0255/2021). https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2021-0255_EN.html
- European Union. (2006a). MEDA Programme, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/meda-programme.html>
- European Union. (2006b). European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument (2007 - 2013), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/european-neighbourhood-and-partnership-instrument-2007-2013.html>
- Frelick, B., Kysel, I. M., and Podkul, J. 2016. “The Impact of Externalisation of Migration Controls on the Rights of Asylum Seekers and Other.” *Journal of Migration and Human Security*, 4 (4): 190–220.
- Gökalp Aras, N. E. 2019a. “Coercive Engineered Syrian Mass Migration in the EU–Turkey Relations: A Case Analysis for Future Reference,” *International Migration*. Vol.57(2): 186–99, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/imig.12566>
- Gökalp Aras, N. E. 2019b. “A Game Changer in EU–Turkey Relations: The Opportunities and Pitfalls of Migration Policy”, *The International Spectator*, Vol. 54(4), p. 44–61, <https://www.iai.it/it/publicazioni/game-changer-eu-turkey-relations-opportunities-andpitfalls-migration-policy>
- Gökalp Aras, N. E. (2021). “The European Union’s Externalisation Policy in the Field of Migration and Asylum: Turkey as a Case Study”. Report Multi-level Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond Project (#770564, Horizon2020) Working Paper Series, Available at <https://www.respondmigration.com/wp-blog/>
- Gökalp Aras, N. E. (2024). “Readmission Agreements and the Evolving Landscape of the Externalised EU Return Policies: The Case of Turkey” in GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13134114, https://zenodo.org/records/13134114/files/D2.2_GAPs_WP2_%20Externalisation%20Working%20Paper_TR.pdf?download=1
- Greenhill, K.M. 2010. *Weapons of Mass Migration: Forced Displacement, Coercion, and Foreign Policy*. The NY: Cornell University Press.
- Halvik, K. (2019). “The Externalisation of EU Migration Policy: A Path Dependent Institution”. Unpublished MA Dissertation. <https://www.duo.uio.no/bitstream/handle/10852/73220/Master-Thesis-Kristina-Hallvik--The-Externalization-of-EU-Migration-Policy.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- Holzinger, K. and Schimmelfennig, F. 2012. “Differentiated Integration in The European Union: Many Concepts, Sparse Theory, Few Data”. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 19:2: 292–305.
- Holzinger, K. and Tosun, J. 2019. “Why Differentiated Integration is such A Common Practice in Europe: A Rational Explanation”. *Journal of Theoretical Politics*. Vol. 31(4): 642–659.
- ICMPD. (2019). Readmission Capacity Building Facility (RCBF) – Annual report 2018.
- ICMPD. (2025a). ERRIN: European Return and Reintegration Network, <https://www.icmpd.org/our-work/projects/european-return-and-reintegration-network-errin>

- ICMPD. (2025b). Migration Partnership Facility (MPF). <https://www.migrationpartnershipfacility.eu/>
- IPOL. 2015. "EU Cooperation with Third Countries in the Field of Migration. European Parliament Study Publications". <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/supportinganalyses>
- Jessop, B. (2010). "Cultural Political Economy and Critical Policy Studies." *Critical Policy Studies*, 3(3-4), 336-356, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/19460171003619741>
- Kassoti, E., & Carrozzini, A. (2022). One instrument in search of an author: Revisiting the authorship and legal nature of the EU–Turkey Statement. In E. Kassoti & N. Idriz (Eds.), *The informalisation of the EU's external action in the field of migration and asylum* (pp. 237–258). T.M.C. Asser Press, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/Delivery.cfm/SSRN_ID3889480_code2495528.pdf?abstractid=3889480&mirid=1
- Lahlou, M. & Belhaj, K. (2025). Infrastructure for Returns /Readmission from EU Member States to Morocco, GAPs Project Morocco Country Snapshot, https://zenodo.org/records/15856666/files/D3.1_WP3_Morocco_snapshot.pdf?download=1
- Lascoumes, P., & Le Galès, P. (2007). Introduction: Understanding public policy through its instruments—From the nature of instruments to the sociology of public policy instrumentation. *Governance*, 20(1), 1–21, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/j.1468-0491.2007.00342.x>
- Laube, L. (2021). "Diplomatic Side-Effects of the EU's Externalisation of Border Control and the Emerging Role of "Transit States"" in Migration Diplomacy." *Historical Social Research* 46 (3): 78-105. doi: 10.12759/hsr.46.2021.3.78-105.
- Lavenex, S., & Uçarer, E. M. (2002). The External Dimension of European Union Immigration Policy. In S. Lavenex & E. M. Uçarer (Eds.), *Migration and the Externalities of European Integration* (pp. 113–132). Lexington Books.
- Lavenex, S., & Uçarer, E. M. (2004). The external dimension of Europeanization: Exporting EU migration policies to neighbouring countries. *Cooperation and Conflict*, 39(4), 417–443. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0010836704047582>
- Lavenex, S. (2006). eShifting Up and Out: The Foreign Policy of European Immigration Control. *West European Politics*, 29(2), 329–350. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402380500512684>
- Lavenex, S. 2015. "The External Face of Differentiated Integration: Third Country Participation in EU Sectoral Bodies". *Journal of European Public Policy*. 22(6): 836–853.
- Leuffen, D, Rittberger, B and Schimmelfennig, F. (2013). *Differentiated Integration: Explaining Variation in the European Union*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- McGregor, E., Godin, M., Gabrielsen Jumbert, M., & Ike, N. (2025). "Conditionality, Compensation, or Both? Comparative Experiences of Third-country Cooperation on Migration with the EU." *Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies*, 23(1), 47–61, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/15562948.2024.2431067>
- Müftüler Baç, M. 2019. Turkey and the European Union: External Differentiated Integration or a Transactional Relationship? Paper prepared for the EUSA Conference. Denver, 9–11 May. <https://eustudies.org/conference/papers/download/633>
- Mügge, D. (2016). "Studying Macroeconomic Indicators as Powerful Ideas." *Journal of European Public Policy*, 23(3), 410-427, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13501763.2015.1115537>
- Natorski, M. (2008). The Meda Programme in Morocco 12 years on: results, experiences and trends, Documentos CIDOB Mediterráneo 11 <https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/90469/The%20Meda%20Programme%20in%20Morocco.pdf>
- Nicolosi, S. F. (2024). "Externalisation of Migration Controls: A Taxonomy of Practices and Their Implications in International and European Law." *Netherlands International Law Review*, 71(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40802-024-00253-9>

- Okuyay, S., Lavenex, S., Krizic, I. and Aydın-Düzgit, S. (2020). “External Differentiation in Migration: Boosting or Hollowing Out the Common EU Policy?” https://www.iai.it/sites/default/files/euidea_pp_10.pdf
- Oxfam. (2023). From development to deterrence? Migration spending under the EU Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI) [Briefing paper]. Oxfam International. <https://doi.org/10.21201/2023.621536>
- Ovacik, G., Ineli-Ciger, M., Ulusoy, O., & Spijkerboer, T. (2022). ASILE Global Asylum Governance and the European Union’s Role: Turkey Country Report. ASILE Project. <https://www.asileproject.eu/>
- Pope, S., & Weisner, Z. (2023). From development to deterrence? Migration spending under the EU Neighbourhood Development and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI). Oxfam. <https://doi.org/10.21201/2023.621536>
- Şahin Mencütek, Z., Gökalp Aras, N. E., Kaya, A., and Rottmann, S. (2023). *Syrian Refugees in Turkey: Between Reception and Integration*, Springer, IMISCOE Research Series. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-031-27366-7>
- Schimmelfennig, F. & Sedelmeier, U. 2004 “Governance by Conditionality: The Europeanization of Central and Eastern Europe”. *Journal of European Public Policy*. 11(4): 661–679.
- Schimmelfennig, F., Leuffen, D. and Rittberger, B. 2015. “The European Union as a System of Differentiated Integration: Interdependence, Politicisation and Differentiation”. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 22(6): 764–782.
- Strik, T., & Robbesom, R. (2024). “Compliance or Complicity? An Analysis of the EU–Tunisia Deal in the Context of the Externalisation of Migration Control.” *Netherlands International Law Review*, 71(2), 199–225. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40802-024-00251-x>
- Stubb, A. C. 1996. “A Categorisation of Differentiated Integration.” *Journal of Common Market Studies*. 34(2): 283–295, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/j.1468-5965.1996.tb00573.x>
- Sum, N. L., & Jessop, B. (2013). *Towards a Cultural Political Economy: Putting Culture in Its Place in Political Economy*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Trauner, F., & Kruse, I. (2008). “EC Visa Facilitation and Readmission Agreements: A New Standard EU Foreign Policy Tool?” *European Journal of Migration and Law*, 10(4), 411–438. <https://doi.org/10.1163/157181608X384687>
- Tsourapas, G. 2017. “Migration Diplomacy in the Global South: Cooperation, Coercion and Issue Linkage in Gaddafi’s Libya.” *Third World Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2017.1350102>
- Tsourdi, E. L., Zardo, F., & Sayed, N. (2023, 3 April). Funding the EU’s External Migration Policy: “Same old” or Potential for Sustainable Collaboration? European Policy Centre Discussion Paper. European Policy Centre. https://www.epc.eu/content/PDF/2023/Funding_the_EUs_external_migration_policy.pdf
- Tsourdi, E. L., & Zardo, F. (2025). “Migration governance through funding: Theoretical, normative, and empirical perspectives.” *Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies*, 23(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15562948.2024.2407584>
- Ulusoy, O. (2025). “Financing Externalisation: The role that EU Funds Play in Shaping the Turkish Asylum and Migration Policies.” *Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies*, 23(1), 91–103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15562948.2024.2407156>
- Uzomah, N. L., & Madu, I. A. (2025) “Reassessing Return Migration Governance: Insights on Nigeria’s Return Migration Infrastructures.” WP3 Country Dossier” in GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. Working paper 2025/13. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15222377, https://zenodo.org/records/15222377/files/D3.1_WP3_Nigeria%20Dossier.pdf?download=1

- Vollmer, R. and Şahin Mencütek, Z. (2023). “Experimentation and Extraction in Reintegration Governance: the case of Kosovo,” *Sozialpolitik*, Vol. 2/2023, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18753/2297-8224-4548>
- Xanthopoulou, E. (2024). “Mapping EU Externalisation Devices Through a Critical Eye.” *European Journal of Migration and Law*, 26(1), 108–135. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718166-12340170>

About the Authors

Dr. N. Ela Gökalp-Aras is a Senior Researcher at the Swedish Research Institute in Istanbul (SRII), Sweden/Turkey. She is the Principal Investigator (PI) and co-leader of WP2 (Legal and Policy Frameworks of Returns in the EU) of the GAPs Project. She is a postdoctoral researcher on the PHOENIX: Human Mobility, Global Challenges, and Resilience in an Age of Social Stress Project. She has a BA in International Relations (Ankara University), an MSc in Climate Change and Development (University of London, SOAS), and an MSc and a PhD in Sociology (Middle East Technical University). She has over twenty-five years of experience in EU-funded research, project coordination, and policy-oriented scholarship, with a particular focus on EU migration and asylum governance, externalisation, return and readmission policies, border management, and EU-Turkey relations. She is one of the editors of the International Journal of Human Mobility (IJHM).

Umutcan Yüksel is a Researcher at the Swedish Research Institute in Istanbul (SRII) and Policy Leader Fellow at the European University Institute (EUI), focusing on the political economy of migration governance and donor decision-making in humanitarian funding allocation. With over 10 years of experience in forced displacement and humanitarian protection, he has worked with various national think tanks and international organisations, including European Commission Humanitarian Aid (ECHO), Welthungerhilfe, German Development Cooperation (GIZ), and Diakonie Katastrophenhilfe. He founded Integrity Consulting to advance localisation and evidence-based humanitarian programming.

Copyright Clause: This work is licensed by the GAPs Consortium under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License, 2020. For details, see <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

GAPs Consortium

Uppsala University (Sweden, Co-Coordinator)
 Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (Germany, Co-Coordinator)
 Stichting Radboud University (Netherlands)
 Özyeğin University (Turkey)
 Hammurabi Human Rights Organisation (Iraq)
 Swedish Research Institute in Istanbul (Sweden/Turkey)
 Hashemite University (Jordan)
 Ethniko Kentro Koinonikon Erevnon (Greece)
 Association Migration Internationale (Morocco)
 Toronto Metropolitan University (Canada)
 University of Nigeria (Nigeria)
 Bilim Organisation for Research and Social Studies (Afghanistan)
 University of Warsaw (Poland)
 Migration Matters EV (Germany)
 University of Sousse (Tunisia)
 SPIA UG (Germany)
 University of Glasgow (UK, Associated Partner)